

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**STUDY TO KNOW INDICATIONS OF LABOUR INDUCTION
OUTCOME AND ITS SHORTFALLS, AUDIT AT NISHTER
HOSPITAL, MULTAN**¹Dr. Basil Siddique, ²Dr. Mohamed Ahmed Abdelmoneam Ramadan, ³Dr. Sehar Sabir¹Lahore Medical and Dental College²Women Wellness Research Center, Hamad Medical Corporation, Qatar³Sir Ganga Ram Hospital**Abstract:**

Objective: The purpose of the supervision is to ensure that the operation and indications of the induction of labor in our hospital are briefly observed and that the process meets certain standards to make changes to ensure that the induction is only when it is time to be relieved. This will help to improve our local standard for induction of labor and therefore patient care.

Study design: A retrospective audit.

Location and duration: Nishter Hospital Multan, Department of Obstetrics and Gynecology, March 2016 to March 2017.

Methodology: The study was conducted at the Nishter Hospital, Multan to observe the indications, the outcome of the induction of the process and birth, and see if it fits the NICE guideline for labor induction. All patients with a single pregnancy at 34 weeks of gestation were included in the trial. Induction, method and delivery induction (IOL) results were evaluated and evaluated in all patients.

Findings: The overall rate of induction in our hospital was 42%. The success rate of job induction was 78%. The main indications for caesarean section were fetal distress and delivery induction failed. Both factors were evaluated in detail. Regarding the failure of the workforce, induction of labor for post-caesarean dates was 40 weeks or more, but 41 weeks before. Similarly, patients with prepartum rupture (RPM) in the absence of chorioamnionitis were induced at 6 hours instead of 24 hours. Range induction has not been considered as an alternative option.

Conclusion: the recommendations are based on this essay and it is recommended that they be reviewed again in the near future to see the implementation of the recommendations.

Key words: Induction of labor force, fetal distress, induction of labor.

*** Corresponding author:****Dr. Basil Siddique,**

Lahore Medical and Dental College

QR code

Please cite this article in press Basil Siddique et al., *Study to Know Indications of Labour Induction Outcome and Its Shortfalls, Audit At Nishter Hospital, Multan., Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2018; 05(08).*

INTRODUCTION:

Induction of labor induction of uterine contraction is progressively cervical dilation and then using mechanical or pharmacological methods to generate delivery spontaneously arranged before the beginning of the spontaneous. The induction rate of the workforce ranges from 9.5% to 33.7% of all pregnancies in the year. The rate of induction is defined as 25% in the developed countries (lowest 4.5% in Niger, highest 35% in Srilanka). Induction of labor in our country is a common procedure. The exact rate of induction of work in our country is unknown; However, it is defined up to 40% in some institutions. Meta-analysis has shown that the induction of labor is associated with less perinatal death in post-date pregnancies when compared to expected management. However, uterine rupture with uterine hyperstimulation and fetal distress and an additional high rate of cesarean section may be more painful for women, which is an important pressure on maternity labor, which requires close monitoring of the risk. This leads to an increase in the use of analgesics and other analgesics.⁸ Therefore, this process should be monitored regularly. We will observe and observe the results of induction of retrospective control of labor inductions carried out in the Nishter Hospital, Multan during the purpose of the 2016-17 audit, and to observe and observe the results of the induction of labor and inducement of the various methods used for the induction and application of post induction methods (NICE Guidance 70).

METHODS:

A total of 220 patients were induced and Study conducted in Nishter Hospital Multan, Department of

Table I : Gestational age at IOL

Gestational age (weeks)	No. of patients
35	20
36	24
37	15
38	30
39	40
40	35
41	56

(N = 160) were induced in induction mode, 73% were induced in gland and E2 in 18% (n = 40) were induced with prostate and 9% (n = 20). The most common indicator for induction of labor in our cohort was 37% (Table II and III).

Obstetrics and Gynecology, March 2016 to March 2017.

Inclusion criteria: Patients who had a single pregnancy in pregnancy. Included in the study were 34 weeks planned for induction.

Exclusion criteria: Pregnant women who were exposed to more than 34 weeks of labor at the start of pregnancy or pregnancy were removed from the study. Data collection and analysis: All patients who met the criteria included in the study and underwent labor induction were included in the study. Patients scheduled for induction were accepted, bishop scores scored and CTG performed. The induction mode was decided according to the bishop's score. The data were collected by the hospital's birth records. All variables such as maternal age, parity, gestational age at induction, indication of labor induction, method of delivery induction, mode of delivery and delivery interval were recorded. induction, and evaluation were evaluated. Ethical approval for research was sought from the institutional ethics committee.

RESULTS:

The mean age of the patient was 29 years. Of the patients, 23% (n = 54) were primigravida while 76% (n = 166) were multigravida. 4% (n = 9) of the total of the patients who had been induced had a previous cesarean delivery. Regarding the age of pregnancy; At the 41st gestational week, 25.4% (n = 56) were induced. During the 37-40 weeks of gestation, 54.5% (n = 120) and 20% (n = 44) were induced before 37 weeks. (Table I, Figure 1)

Table II: Indications for IOL

Indication of IOL	No of patients	%
PPROM	16	7%
PIH	34	15%
GDM	19	9%
FGR	24	11%
Postdates	82	37%
PROM	14	6%
Oligohydramnios	18	8%
Maternal wish	13	6%

Table III: Outcome of IOL

Outcome of IOL	No of patients	%
NVD	163	74
CS	48	22
Instrumental delivery	9	4

The induction interval was 6-12 hours in 59% of cases, 0-6 hours in 27% of cases and 12-18 hours in 14%. Uterine hyperstimulation or uterine rupture. Cesarean section indications failed between caesarean section births. IOL, fetal distress and secondary arrest. (table IV, figure 4)

Table IV: Indication of CS among IOL patients

Indication of CS among IOL	NO. of patients
Failed IOL	19
Fetal Distress	21
Failure to progress	08

factor was assessed in more detail and found to be the cause of the failed IOL postdates of the caesarean section of birth "IOL failed" (7), FGR (5), PPRM (4) and DM (2), figure 5)

Table V: Indication of IOL among those who underwent CS for Failed IOL

Indication of IOL among those who underwent CS for Failed IOL	No. of patients
IUGR	05
PROM	04
POSTDATES	07
DM	02
Others	01

Table V: Indication of IOL among those who underwent CS for Failed IOL

DISCUSSION:

The overall rate of induction in our hospital is 42%, which is higher than other hospitals, but it can be justified because it is a referral center for higher education and is applied to high-risk pregnancies. There are various methods for induction of labor, but the most commonly used method in our hospital is the prostaglandin gel / prostine tablet recommended by NICE. This audit shows good agreement with the NICE directives in many directions as regards the decision made by the consultant, the timing and the induction desire. The most common indication for induction of labor in our hospital was subsequently 37%, followed by pregnancy-induced hypertension at 15%. In another study in Maiduguri in Nigeria, the common indications for induction of labor were the same, but 46.8% and 33% for the next appointment, although the frequency was higher than the one in our study. 5% for hypertension caused by your pregnancy Bukola et al. The most common indications are prelabor rupture and hypertension in pregnancy. The success rate for induction was 78% in our hospital.

This rate is higher than 70.3% reported in the United States, 81% at Agha Khan University and slightly lower than that reported at public health facilities. Fetal distress and unsuccessful induction were the two main causes of cesarean delivery in our control. Lewani et al. They reported fetal distress and prolonged delivery as the main causes of cesarean section in invasive patients. We evaluate these two factors in detail, and we keep the NICE rules as a standard. Due to fetal distress, CTG is the only device available for fetal monitoring. Although the positive predictive value of CTG is low, suspicious CTG usually leads to a cesarean, which is contradictory to guidelines recommending that CTG is not used for decision making and that it should be used in a meaningful sampling of the underlying meconium. Fetal. Between failed IOLs, IOLs after cesarean section, IOL was performed 40 weeks but 41 weeks before, and we found that there was no routine membrane cleaning for pregnancies after 40. 40 + 6 weeks. Likewise, women with PROM were immediately alerted, even in the absence of

chorioamnionitis (within 6 hours). Intermittent induction is not considered an alternative option in all cases. Haq et al. In a study conducted at the PAAB Islamabad hospital, delivery induction at 41 weeks was associated with higher vaginal deliveries (89% vs 71%) compared with IOL at 40 weeks. 17 We have some recommendations to improve the outcome of the job, as maintaining the SAFETY guidelines as a standard is related to a better outcome of the emergence of labor as a result of the guidelines.

High Fetal monitoring of high-risk pregnancies should be completed with a lethal blood sampling, since the positive predictive value of CTG is low. Subseal IOL for subsequent appointments should have 41 weeks of age supported by 40-40 + 6 weeks of erasing membranes. In the absence of chorioamnionitis in OM PROM, it can be administered 24 hours before the birth trial. Interval induction should be maintained as an option for elective low risk induction.

REFERENCES:

1. Akhtar, N., 2018. Induction of Labour Audit-Fauji Foundation Hospital Rawalpindi. *Journal of the Society of Obstetrics and Gynaecologists of Pakistan*, 6(3), pp.129-132.
2. McGuane, Jonathan T., Lori Grlj, and Michael J. Peek. "Obesity, gestational diabetes and macrosomia are associated with increasing rates of early-term induction of labour at The Canberra Hospital." *Australian and New Zealand Journal of Obstetrics and Gynaecology* (2018).
3. Beckmann, Michael, Emma Paterson, and Ashleigh Smith. "Redesigning induction of labour processes." *Australian and New Zealand Journal of Obstetrics and Gynaecology* 58, no. 3 (2018): 315-320.
4. Barnfield, L., Neale, E. and Reynolds, S., 2018. Outpatient cervical ripening in a district general hospital: a five-year retrospective cohort study. *Journal of Obstetrics and Gynaecology*, 38(3), pp.301-304.
5. King, Kristina, Jinny Foo, Kirsty Hazelton, and Amanda Henry. "Selective versus universal third trimester ultrasound: Time for a rethink? An audit of current practices at a metropolitan Sydney hospital." *Australasian Journal of Ultrasound in Medicine* 21, no. 2 (2018): 96-103.
6. Tomlinson, Antony John, Elizabeth Martindale, Karen Bancroft, and Alexander Heazell. "Improved management of stillbirth using a care pathway." *International Journal of Health Governance* 23, no. 1 (2018): 18-37.
7. Soman, Sruthy, Sobha S. Nair, J. N. Janani, K. Radhamany, and Ann John Kurien. "OASIS: clinical audit in a tertiary care centre." *International Journal of Reproduction, Contraception, Obstetrics and Gynecology* 7, no. 5 (2018): 1958-1962.
8. Tura, Abera Kenay, Olga Pijpers, Myrna de Man, Myrthe Cleveringa, Ingeborg Koopmans, Tadesse Gure, and Jelle Stekelenburg. "Analysis of caesarean sections using Robson 10-group classification system in a university hospital in eastern Ethiopia: a cross-sectional study." *BMJ open* 8, no. 4 (2018): e020520.
9. Bermúdez-Tamayo, Clara, Mira Johri, and Nils Chaillet. "Budget impact of a program for safely reducing caesarean sections in Canada." *Midwifery* 60 (2018): 20-26.
10. Imtiaz, R., Husain, S. and Izhar, R., 2018. Adoption of Robson's Ten Group Classification System (RTGCS) to Analyse Caesarean Section Rates at a Tertiary Care Centre in Pakistan. *Annals of Abbasi Shaheed Hospital & Karachi Medical & Dental College*, 23(1).
11. Nettle, J.A., Mcnamara, H.C. and Du Plessis, J.M., 2018. Perineal trauma with vaginal birth after a previous caesarean section: A retrospective cohort study. *Australian and New Zealand Journal of Obstetrics and Gynaecology*.
12. Radhika, Kondareddy, and Triveni Kondareddy. "Use of the Robson classification to assess caesarean section trends in tertiary hospital." *International Journal of Reproduction, Contraception, Obstetrics and Gynecology* 7, no. 5 (2018): 1796-1800.
13. Smith, G. C. S. (2018). Should we implement universal screening with late pregnancy ultrasound to prevent stillbirth?. *BJOG: An International Journal of Obstetrics & Gynaecology*, 125(2), 101-103.
14. Prosser, Samantha J., Adrian G. Barnett, and Yvette D. Miller. "Factors promoting or inhibiting normal birth." *BMC pregnancy and childbirth* 18, no. 1 (2018): 241.